

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LISTENING SKILLS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL STUDENTS

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The Relationship between Listening Skills and Academic Performance of Entrepreneurial Students

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Abstract

This study made use of a survey questionnaire to find out the relationship between the listening skills and academic performance of entrepreneurial students. The respondents were 80 students who were officially enrolled in school year 2022-2023 in Davao de Oro State College. Using the questionnaire on the listening skills adapted from HURIER Listening tool and Pearson r correlation coefficient as the statistical tool, it was found out that students' listening skills was rated in the outstanding level and the academic performance of the students were categorized as satisfactory level. The results also showed that there was no significant relationship between the academic performance and listening skills in receiving, understanding, remembering, evaluating and responding. There was no significant correlation found in this study, so more research is needed to ascertain whether additional elements may have an impact on students' listening abilities in general and academic performance in particular.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial students, listening skill, hearing, understanding, remembering, interpreting*

Introduction

The skill of listening is the first linguistic skill that humans acquire. Perhaps given its primary placement among linguistic skills, the many definitions of listening differ. In general, however, listening comprises sending a message (i.e., transmission), hearing that message, and making sense of it (Ozby, 2005). Listening and speaking skills are not significant parts of many books and teachers do not consider these skills in their classes. Many pupils struggle with reading comprehension, which can seriously impact a child's performance in all subject areas. Reading comprehension issues cause students to frequently perform significantly worse academically than their peers in a variety of subjects. It is believed that listening is particularly important communication tool for entrepreneurs who are continuously seeking information and support for their business ideas. Active listening allows the individual to hear what is being said.

In the study conducted in Turkey entitled "Active Listening Strategies of Academically Successful University Students" revealed that academically successful university students used different cognitive, affective, and psychomotor-based strategies in practicing active listening (Canpolat, Kuzu, Yildirim, & Canpolat (2015).

Furthermore, in the Philippines, a study conducted by Viola-Bangelisan (2018) claimed that the respondents' speaking and listening skills revealed a high significance, which can be deduced that the respondents are not effective communicators and it also revealed that the respondents' communicative competence was highly significant relative to their grades in English. Hence, addressing the gap, a Communication Enhancement Program was proposed to address the speaking and listening needs of the respondents.

In Lyceum of the Philippines University-Laguna, for academic institutions, retention of students has become a challenging issue (Curbano, 2020). Instructors in Davao De Oro State College-New Bataan Branch seek to look for the root cause as to why Entrepreneurship students are having challenges with listening during class discussion. They have the problem on understanding and retaining topics discussed in class which resulted to low academic performance. Many teachers commented that these students are slow in retention due to lack of listening skill. The Entrepreneurial students of Davao De Oro State College possess excessive noise reduces the ability to hear lessons clearly and has a negative effect on their ability to learn. They easily forget what has been taught and could hardly recall their lessons and this is the very reason why the researcher is prompted to conduct this study that aims to determine if the listening skills of the entrepreneurship students of Davao De Oro State College-New Bataan Branch affect their academic performance.

Research Questions

The aim of the study is to determine the influence of the listening skill on the academic performance of the 80 second-year BS Entrepreneurship students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the listening skills of the second year BS Entrepreneurship students in terms of:
 - 1.1. receiving,
 - 1.2. understanding,
 - 1.3. remembering,
 - 1.4. evaluating, and
 - 1.5. responding?
2. What is the level of the academic performance of the second year BS Entrepreneurship students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between listening skills and academic performance of the second year BS Entrepreneurship students?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research refers to techniques that outline the features of the examined variables. Using this methodology, the emphasis is more on answering "what" questions than "why" questions about the study. Instead of concentrating on the "why," the goal of this descriptive research is to report the characteristics of the demographic understudy simply. It is quantitative because it tries to gather and quantitatively analyzed data. This study is an effective research method that enables the researcher to gather data and, using statistical analysis, describe the demographics of the data (Voxco, 2021). A research design known as a correlational study examines the connections between two or more variables. Since correlational studies are not experiments, no variables are changed or under the experimenter's control (Cherry, 2022).

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 80 second year BS Entrepreneurship students who were enrolled in Davao De Oro State College-New Bataan Brach for school year 2022-2023. The researcher used the purposive sampling technique, a non-probability sampling method which involves examining the whole group. In this regard the researcher purposively selected two sections from the five sections in Entrepreneurship.

Instruments

The questionnaire on the listening skills was adapted from HURRIER Listening tool . Some of the questions were modified appropriated for this study. There were five questions in each indicator with a total number of 36 questions. Further, the academic performance of the students was measured by a 60-item teacher-made test. A table of specifications was prepared to show the distribution of the questions based on the levels of cognitive domain.

There were five validators assigned to validate the questionnaire to test its validity and reliability. After which the questionnaire was modified based on the suggestions and recommendations of the validators. After the modification of the questionnaire, it was reproduced and administered to the respondents of the study according to its specified schedules. Further, the set of questionnaire was piloted to other group of students who were not involved in the study.

Procedure

Before proceeding with the study, a letter request from the Office of the Dean of the Graduate School of Assumption College of Nabunturan was prepared for the College President in Davao de Oro to allow the researcher to conduct the study. After the approval, the researcher again asked the same permission from the school president of DDOSC. After the approval and the validation of the questionnaire, the researcher administered it to the 80 second year BS Entrepreneurship students.

To facilitate more reliable responses, the researcher explained very clearly to the student respondents what to do with the questionnaire. The items in each of the five indicators in listening skills were explained to them. No copies of the research questionnaire left unanswered. Everything would be done inside the classroom under the supervision of the researcher herself. All responses to every item were carefully tallied, collated, and recorded. Statistical tools were applied based on the problems of the study, and these were interpreted logically.

Data Analysis

The following tools were used to aid for the statistical interpretation of data:

1. Frequency, Percentage, and Average will be used to determine the level of listening skills and the academic performance of the students.
2. To test the significant relationship between the listening skills and the academic performance of the students, Pearson r correlation coefficient will be used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation obtained from the gathered data in Listening Skill competence and Academic performance.

The level of Students' Listening Skills based on hearing, understanding, remembering, interpreting, evaluating, and responding.

Table 1 presents the level of students' Listening Skill competence from different competencies.

Table 1 reveals the level of students' listening skills in different competencies. The class proficiency for hearing is 74.3%, which shows

outstanding level of their performance; understanding which is 73%, very satisfactory; remembering which is 74%, outstanding; interpreting which is 73.3%, very satisfactory, evaluating which is 75%, outstanding and responding which is 74%, very satisfactory. Overall results reveal that the class proficiency is 74%; for the skill mastery is nearing mastery; class achievement is 90% and the performance level of the students is outstanding which imply that most of the students possess exceptional skills and qualities when it comes to actively and attentively receiving and comprehending what others are saying.

Table 1. *Level of Students' Listening Skill*

	<i>Hearing (30)</i>	<i>Understanding (30)</i>	<i>Remembering (30)</i>	<i>Interpreting (30)</i>	<i>Evaluating (30)</i>	<i>Responding(30)</i>	<i>Total</i>
Valid	80	81	81	81	81	81	81
Missing	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	22.313	21.863	22.350	22.000	22.387	22.163	133.075
Std. Dev	4.205	3.879	4.075	4.447	3.803	3.998	21.760
Minimum	9.000	14.000	14.000	11.000	9.000	14.000	81.000
Maximum	30.000	29.000	30.000	30.000	30.000	30.000	176.000
Class Proficiency	74.3%	73%	74.%	73.3%	75%	74%	74%
Skill Mastery	Nearing	Nearing	Nearing	Nearing	Master	Nearing	Nearing
Achievement	90%	89%	90%	89%	90%	89%	90%
Performance Level	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Outstanding

The results suggest that they show empathy and understanding towards the thoughts, feelings, and perspectives of the speaker. They understand what the speaker is conveying and that they can feel what the speaker feels. With this they are able to see their own perspective and relate it to the perspective of others. They are able to enhance more their communication skill and by this the quality of communication strengthens and able to build good relationship with others. Through communication, they participate in problem solving activities which are facilitated by their instructors.

The Level of Students Academic Performance

It is presented in Table 2 the level of students' academic performance.

Table 2. *Level of Students' Academic Performance*

<i>Level of Academic Performance (60)</i>	
Valid	81
Missing	0
Mean	34.538
Std. Dev	7.852
Minimum	14.000
Maximum	53.000
Proficiency	58%
Skill Mastery	Neary
Achievement	83%
Performance Level	Satisfactory

Table 2 reveals the level of students' academic performance of which the class proficiency is 58%, which shows satisfactory performance. Based on the result, the students meet the minimum requirements or standards set by the institution. It suggests

that a student has performed adequately or sufficiently to pass a course or meet the basic expectations for that particular academic task. In most grading systems, "satisfactory" may be represented by a passing grade (e.g., C or equivalent) that indicates the student has met the necessary criteria to progress or complete a course or assignment. It implies that the student has demonstrated a basic understanding of the subject matter and has fulfilled the essential requirements.

Significant Relationship Between Students Listening Skill and Academic Performance

The table 3 presents the relationship of the students' listening skill and academic performance.

Table 3. *Relationship Between Students Listening Skill and Academic Performance*

<i>Person's Correlations</i>		
<i>Variable</i>	<i>Level of Listening Skill (65) Level of Academic Performance (20)</i>	
Level of Listening Skill	Pearson's r	
	p-value	
Level of Academic Performance	Pearson's r	-0.208
	p-value	0.062

The level of Students' Listening Skill Competence. The overall result of the listening skills of students has an outstanding level with 74% class proficiency which implies that students have exceptional listening skills and show that their performance is interpreted as in mastery level. If children are to develop good listening habits, they must perceive that the teacher expects them to listen. Properly setting the stage for listening will significantly enhance the development of those perceptions. Good listening can be reinforced in the classroom by allowing the children (rather than the teacher) to restate questions, directions, explanations, or other children's answers. Also, children should have the opportunity to answer questions and engage in open dialogue. Teachers need not personally answer every question asked by the children, because this destroys an excellent opportunity to provide meaningful oral and listening experiences for the other members of the class Funk, H. D., & Funk, G. D.(1989).

The level of students' academic performance. The level of students' academic performance is 58% for class proficiency and 83% for the achievement level which is interpreted as satisfactory. Satisfactory in a course scheduled on a "Satisfactory-Unsatisfactory" basis shall be defined as the equivalent of "D" or better on the conventional grading system (A-B-C-D-F) in that course. Quality points for "Satisfactory-Unsatisfactory" courses shall not be tabulated toward the student's grade average; however, credit shall be recorded toward his total credit requirements if he passes the course. An Unsatisfactory grade shall receive neither credit nor quality points. If the grade is Unsatisfactory, a course may be taken again, but only under the conventional grading system (A-B-C-D-F). Since the Satisfactory-Unsatisfactory system was implemented in Fall 1968, it has become increasingly popular among the students of the College of Business Administration. Enrollments in courses taken on a "Satisfactory-Unsatisfactory" grading basis have increased from 275 in the Fall of 1968 to 562 in the Fall of 1969. An increasing number of accounting courses have been scheduled by accounting majors on a "Satisfactory-Unsatisfactory" basis (Carpenter & Strawser, 1971).

Significant relationship between students' listening skill and academic performance. It was revealed that there is no significant relationship between the listening skills of the students and their academic performance. The result is an indication that the students' listening skills do not affect the academic performance of the students. In terms of achievement, class has an achievement level of 89% which is described as VS according to D.O. no. 8, series of 2015.

Karaduz (2010) has found that students do not use listening strategies that are too multifarious. Using limited stimulation in learning environments, being rendered passive in traditional education systems, and being unable to develop sufficient strategies can cause them to become individuals who only take notes, listen to the instructor quietly, are shy about objecting, and cannot develop alternative ideas. Furthermore, Karaduz (2010) reiterated that other than the verbal channel, by which students can express themselves in multiple learning activities, listening environments should also allow other senses to be used as well. Though most classroom communication revolves around instructor's speeches, the four sensory channels other than listening—namely, sight, touch, taste, and smell—can facilitate or hinder learning in normal classrooms. As such, new forms of stimulation can be provided by shifting sensory channels, though realizing such changes requires students to be primed for those sensory experiences.

Conclusions

The results of the data analysis utilizing Pearson r correlation led to the conclusion that there was no significant relationship between the students' academic performance and their listening skills. In terms of the level of students' academic performance, 58% for class proficiency and 83% for the achievement level which is interpreted as satisfactory. For level of students' academic performance, the result show i58% for class proficiency and 83% for the achievement level which is interpreted as satisfactory. This means that students who used listening strategies more frequently did not necessarily affect their academic performance although listening can facilitate better understanding of the lesson presented by the teacher. It also suggests that listening skill is not the only factor that could affect the performance of the students in terms of academics.

The Commission on Higher Education and the school administration should provide the teachers seminars and trainings in order to ensure effective teaching and develop the listening skills of the students.

Teachers should be creative in choosing teaching strategies to motivate the students to pay attention and relate to the teacher.

Teachers should also ensure the basic strategies to develop these skills: hearing, understanding, remembering, interpreting, evaluating, and responding to facilitate better understanding of the lesson.

Encourage students to analyze what they learnt from listening to the narrative while concentrating on the main understanding objectives.

Students must be engaged in different activities to gain understanding before listening and preview vocabulary words. Invite them to think about relevant prior knowledge, anticipate the subject of the story, or otherwise engage actively in preparing for the story.

Further research should be done to determine what other factors may affect students' listening skills in general and academic achievement in particular, as there was no significant association discovered in this study. While acknowledging the limitations of the current study, it is hoped that future research will yield more accurate findings.

References

Canpolat, M., Sekvan, K. U. Z. U., Yildirim, B., & Canpolat, S. (2015). Active listening strategies of academically successful university

students. Eurasian Journal of Educational Research,15(60), 163-180.

Carpenter, C. G., & Strawser, R. H. (1971). Initial Experience with Satisfactory-Unsatisfactory Grading in Accounting Courses. *The Accounting Review*, 46(1), 160-162.

Cherry, K. (2022). What is a correlational study? Very Well Mind.

Coleman, L., King T., & Turner W. (2022). Five Stages of Listening. Southwest Tennessee Community College.

Colle, T. (2022). Definition of Listening

Curbano, R. J., & Hernandez, N. B. (2020). Modeling the Factors Influencing the Retention Decision of the Students of LPU-Laguna and LPU-St. Cabrini using Students Integration Theory. *institutions*, 4(1).

DeVito, J. A. (2000). *The elements of public speaking* (7th ed.). New York, NY: Longman.

Ergin, Birol (2005). rvlsoft/Shutterstock.com 2 Verbal and Nonverbal

Funk, H. D., & Funk, G. D. (1989). Guidelines for developing listening skills. *The Reading Teacher*, 42(9), 660-663.

Karaduz, A. (2010). Türkçe ve sınıf öğretmeni adaylarının dinleme stratejilerinin değerlei-[The evaluation of listening strategies of Turkish-language and primary student teachers]. *Erciyes Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 29, 39–55.

Leonard, V. (Jul 2020). Bad Listening Practices. The LibreTexts libraries Camp,

Nordquist, R. (2019). The definition of listening and how to do it well. ThoughtCo, Aug, 26, 2020.

Optimist Minds. (August 2022). Pseudo listening vs True listening (Differences)

Ozbay M. (2005). *Bir Dil Becerisi Olarak Dinleme Egitimi*. Ankara: Akcag Basim Yayin Dagitim.

Rothwell, J. Dan. *In the Company of Others*. McGraw-Hill. New York. 2004.

Tyagi, B. (2013). Listening: An important skill and its various aspects. *The Criterion An International Journal in English*, 12(1), 1-8.

Viola-Bangelisan, K. G. *Listening and Speaking Skills of Senior High School: Towards Progressive English Language Communication Program*.

Voxco (2021). *Descriptive Research Design*. <https://www.voxco.com/blog/descriptive-research-design/>

Janusik, L. A., & Wolvin, A. D. (2009). 24 hours in a day: A listening update to the time studies. *The Intl. Journal of Listening*, 23(2), 104-120.

Youth Employment UK. (2020). *Active Listening: Why Is It Important Not To Interrupt?*

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